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Conflict Management Styles of Elementary School Heads and Their Influence to Teachers' Morale

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ABSTRACT

This study focused on the conflict management styles of elementary school heads and their influence to teachers' morale as perceived by the elementary school heads themselves and the elementary teachers in the Division of Puerto Princesa City. Quantitative method of research was employed.

Data were obtained through the use of survey questionnaire. Frequency counts, percentages, mean, weighted mean, Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient r and Korin's Correlation were applied in the treatment of raw data.

Result of the study revealed that collaborating was evident and was the dominant conflict management styles of elementary school heads. As to causes of conflict, both school heads and teachers claimed that the variables under personality factors are the major causes conflicts in school.

Proposed solutions to conflict are respect and obedience, sharing of interest and goals and improved communication. The study revealed that conflict management styles of elementary school heads influence teachers' morale.

Significant difference existed on the perception of both elementary school heads and teachers in terms of collaborating, competing, accommodating and compromising as conflict management styles of elementary school heads. The perception of elementary school heads and teachers are similar in terms of causes of conflicts and proposed solution.

INTRODUCTION

Conflict is certain as long as there is a human element present. Thus, conflict is a pervasive aspect in both social circles and professional interactions. Conflict exists in all human relationships: it always has and probably always will.

Furthermore, individuals who never experience conflict at the workplace are living in a dream world, blind to their surroundings or are confined to solitary confinement. Conflict presently continues to be a factor in academic life. Schools frequently appear to be centers of tension; on occasion, they are perhaps a manifestation of problems in the community.

The term conflict is viewed in a variety of ways because of its confusion with those conditions which lead to situations of different conflict. Thomas (2015) defines conflict as "the process which begins when one party perceives that the other has frustrated, or is about to frustrate, some concern of his".

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At schools conflicts may be experienced in many issues such as distribution of work among personnel, financial resources, in and out of class teaching activities and practices, rewards, punishment, assessment practices, use of power-authority, being late for class, leave of absences, political views, negative personal attitudes, passing grade levels and scoring system, issues regarding the legislation, student behaviors, dress code, assignments and placements for staff and distribution of resources (Karip, 2000). Conflicts can take place between administrators-teachers, teachers-teachers, teachers-students or parents-parents or among the students.

It should be kept in mind that regardless of the type of conflict or the group that take part in it, conflicts will deepen and be more complicated unless they are resolved and people involved in the conflict will experience negative feelings (Argon, 2014).

This will negatively affect the job performances of the personnel and will decrease the quality of education and training at schools. The current study, undertaken in line with the literature, examined and discussed the conflicts experienced at school based on teacher views. In this respect, the study aimed to determine teacher views regarding the conflicts experienced at schools, the reasons behind conflicts, the impact of conflict on teachers and the responses conflict generates.

When there is conflict, there must be a resolution of such conflict. This is where the Conflict Management enters the ring. Ghaffar (2007) quoted the Conflict Resolution Skills/Strategies of David W. Johnson and Roger T. Johnson which hold that Conflict resolution and peer mediation programs are often promoted as a way to reduce violence in schools. Management of conflict is a human relations concept long recognized in business and industry as a necessary component of the developmental process. Sweeney and Caruthers (2015) define conflict resolution in a most general and concise way as the process used by parties in conflict to reach a settlement.

A manager should be able to see emerging conflicts and take appropriate pre-emptive action. The manager should understand the causes creating conflict, the outcome of conflict, and various methods by which conflict can be managed in the organization.

With this understanding, the manager should evolve an approach for resolving conflicts before their disruptive repercussions have an impact on productivity and creativity. Therefore, a manager should possess special skills to react to conflict situations, and should create an open climate for communication between conflicting parties.

The aforementioned paragraphs serve as important reasons why there is a need to conduct this study.

Statement of the Problem

The general aim of this study is to determine the conflict management styles of the elementary school heads in the Division of Puerto Princesa City Specifically, it sought to answer the following aspects of the main problems:

1. What is the demographic profile of the elementary school heads in the Division of Puerto Princesa City in terms of:
 - a. age;
 - b. gender;
 - c. number of years in teaching;
 - d. highest degree earned and;
 - e. attendance to seminar and trainings related to conflict management?
2. How conflict management styles of the elementary school heads describe as perceived by elementary school teachers and elementary school heads themselves in terms of:
 - a. collaborating;
 - b. competing;

- c. avoiding;
 - d. accommodating and;
 - e. compromising?
3. What describes the causes of conflict as perceived by the elementary school heads and elementary school teachers in terms of:
- a. situational factors ;
 - b. personality factors;
 - c. power factors and;
 - d. conflict of interest?
4. What describes the proposed solution to conflict as perceived by the elementary school heads and elementary school teachers in terms of:
- a. improved communication;
 - b. values integration;
 - c. respect
 - and obedience and; d. sharing of interests/goals?
5. How do conflict management styles of the elementary school heads influence the teachers' morale as perceived by the elementary school heads and elementary school teachers?
6. Is there a significant relationship between demographic profile of the elementary school heads and their conflict management styles?
7. Is there a significant relationship between the conflict management styles of elementary school heads and the teachers' morale?
8. Is there a significant relationship between the causes of conflict and proposed solution as perceived by school heads?
9. Is there a significant difference on the perception of the elementary school heads and elementary school teachers in terms of conflict management styles of the elementary school heads?
10. Is there a significant difference on the causes and solution to conflict as perceived by the school heads and elementary school teachers?

Significance of the Study

The study is deemed essential to the following;

Schools. This study is considered important for the schools since conflict is an essential and unavoidable human phenomenon because where there is human interaction; there is a likelihood of personal likes and dislikes.

These agreements and disagreements among individuals and groups lead them to conflicts in schools. Conflicts are neither constructive nor disruptive but the ways these are handled make them either positive or negative.

Schools, like other human organizations, are prone to one or other type of conflict. Various conflict management strategies are adopted for handling conflict; the most important among these are mediation, negotiation, avoidance, collaborating etc. Main thrust of this paper is on the exploration of the nature of conflicts in schools, its causes and techniques adopted for its management.

Schools Division Supervisor. This study will make the following significant contribution to City Schools Division of Puerto Princesa in terms of providing fresh data and study on the schools' conflict management including policy and program adjustments if there is really a need especially in the said division.

Students. This study will eventually benefit the students because a conflict free school or conflict less school will boost the morale of teachers; thus, in return shall be expecting to make students more interested in studying.

School heads. This study can enhance school heads to a better understanding about their existing level of conflict management strategies.

Therefore, from the administration perspective they would come up with new ways to resolving conflict, for example modifying the existing school regulations, adding new and value added members welfare programs, and recognizing the outstanding performances efficiently and fairly.

Teachers. This study will help school principals better understand about the existing conflict among their teachers. Conflict management reduces tensions motivates the employee to give their best to the organizations.

Researchers. This study can help future researchers who will be conducting studies on the conflict management styles of school principals and teachers involvement in conflict resolution.

METHODOLOGY

This section presents the locale of the study, research design, and respondent of the study, sampling procedure, instruments, data collection procedures and data treatment.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted in selected public elementary schools in the Division of Puerto Princesa City. Thirty seven (37) school heads and two hundred sixty four (264) teachers were selected to represent diverse schools, gender, age, education and other profile of school heads.

Research Design

The study utilized the quantitative method. This research method emphasizes objective measurements and the statistical, mathematical, or numerical analysis of data collected through polls, questionnaires, and surveys, or by manipulating pre-existing statistical data using computational techniques.(Best, 2015).

The quantitative method was employed through the use of the survey questionnaire to determine the demographic profile, level of conflict management of school heads, causes of conflict, proposed solution to conflict and influence of conflict management style to teachers' morale.

Likewise, significant relationships and differences were determined between and among variables that were used by the researcher in consolidating findings and formulating conclusions.

Respondents of the Study

Thirty seven (37) public elementary school heads and two hundred sixty four (264) teachers were the respondents of this study from District I, District II and District III schools. Slovin's Formula was used to determine the actual sample size of the respondents.

Sampling Procedure

A master list of public elementary school heads and teachers from the Human Resource Management Office of the Division of Puerto Princesa was used as basis of the study.

Simple random sampling was used in this study wherein each member of the subset of statistical population has an equal probability of being chosen. All the names of elementary school teacher respondents were chosen out of a hat.

In this study, total enumeration of the school heads was employed while the teacher respondents' population was computed using the Slovin's Formula. The researcher shall have a total of thirty seven (37) school heads and two hundred sixty four (264) samples following a 5% margin of error.

Instrumentation

The data for the quantitative aspect of the study was taken from the survey questionnaire.

A survey questionnaire was used in this study which consisted of five (5) parts which include: Part I, Demographic Characteristics, Part II, Conflict Management Styles, and Part III, Common issues which causes conflict among teachers Part IV, Solution to Conflicts Common among Teachers and Part V Teachers' Morale. There are three sets of questionnaires. The first set is intended for the elementary school heads second set is for the teacher respondents.

The basis of the questionnaire was from Gaumer et al., (2016) entitled Conflict Management Questionnaire published by the University of Kansas, United States. This questionnaire served as a reference of the researcher in conducting the respective instrument of this study, hence the researcher modified it to fit in for this study and for the target respondents.

The following rating scales and descriptions were used in analyzing the data. A 5 point rating scale was used to find out the conflict management styles of the elementary school principals.

Likewise, a 5 point rating scale below was used to determine the common issues of conflicts and solutions to conflicts among teachers and teachers' morale.

Reliability of the instrument was assessed via piloting the instrument to Matahimik- Bucana Elementary School headed by teacher-in-charge with 13 teachers. Pilot testing participants were given the instrument to complete and the opportunity to discuss purpose and clarity of items and make suggestions for improvement in both verbal and written form. In addition the questionnaire was submitted to three (3) members of advisory committee.

Data Collection Procedure

A survey questionnaire was used in the gathering of data needed. The researcher personally administered the survey questionnaire to the respondents. All respondents were given time to go over and accomplish the questionnaire.

A letter of request was sent to the Division Superintendent asking permission to conduct the study. The same request was submitted to Public Schools District Supervisor Team Leader.

Treatment of Data

To describe the profile of the elementary school heads and teachers the frequency counts and percentages were employed. Meanwhile mean and weighted mean were employed to assess the elementary school heads' conflict management style and common issues which cause conflict among the teachers. On the other hand, to analyze the relationship between demographic profile of the school heads and their conflict management styles, the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient r was used.

The same statistical treatment was employed to determine the relationship between causes of conflict and the proposed solution. Lastly, to analyze relationship between the conflict management styles of the elementary school heads and teachers' morale Korin's Correlation was used. Lastly, t-test was used to determine the significant difference on the perception of the elementary school heads and teachers in terms of conflict management styles of elementary school heads, causes and proposed solution to conflict.

Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the findings, interpretation and analysis of data specifically in determining the profiles of elementary school heads and teachers in the Division of Puerto Princesa City, the conflict management of school heads and their influence to teachers' morale. Correlations and comparisons between and among variables considered in the study are also highlighted.

Profile of School Elementary School Heads

Table 1 shows the demographic profile of the selected elementary school heads in the Division of Puerto Princesa City.

It can be seen from the table that most of the school heads belonged to the age bracket between 39 and 45 with a frequency of 14 or 37.85 percent. The least number of school heads have ages between 53 to 59 with a frequency of 5 or 13.51 percent.

The mean age of school heads is 44.14, which mean they were on the peak of their career as school manager.

In terms of gender, majority of the school heads are female with a frequency of 26 or 70.27. This means that the schools in the Division Puerto Princesa are managed and under the leadership of woman power.

Eleven or 29.73 percent of the school heads have earned units in Doctoral Degree. More than half of the school heads Masteral Degree holder with a frequency of 23 or 62.16 per cent. Only 3 or 8.11 percent have earned Bachelor's Degree. This implies that the school heads in the Division of Puerto Princesa City were proactive in terms of professional development.

All school heads had attended the School Heads Development Program while 12 or 32.43 percent attended Gender and Equality Seminar. This implies that the numbers of seminar incurred by the school heads regarding conflict management are insufficient.

Table 1. Demographic Profile of the Elementary School Heads in the Division of Puerto Princesa City

Profile	Frequency N=37	Percentage
Age		
53 - 59	5	13.51
46 - 52	9	24.32
39 - 45	14	37.85
32 - 38	9	24.32
Mean	44.14	
Gender		
Female	26	70.27
Male	11	29.73
Highest degree earned		
Doctoral Degree	11	29.73
Masteral Degree	23	62.16
Bachelor's Degree	3	8.11
Attendance to seminars and trainings related to conflict management		
School Heads Development Program	37	100.00
Gender and Equality Seminar	12	32.43

Conflict Management Styles of the Elementary School Heads

Table 2 presents the conflict management styles of the elementary school heads as perceived by themselves and elementary school teachers.

For the school heads, collaborating got the highest rank, under this conflict management style the statement "gather as much information as I can and keep the lines of communication open" ranked first with a mean of 4.62 described as very effective; followed by "attempt to deal with all of his and my concerns, attempt to get all concerns and issues immediately out in the open and share the problem with the other persons so that we can work it out." with a mean of 4.59 described as very effective. The least is "try to see conflict from both sides." with a mean of 4.38 described as effective.

Similarly, teachers gave highest rating under collaborating, the statement “attempt to deal with all of his and my concerns” ranked first with the mean of 4.25 followed by “tell him my ideas and ask him for his ideas”, with the mean of 4.23.

The top two statements were described as effective. The statement that got the lowest mean was “try to see conflict from both sides” with mean of 4.02 described as effective.

This implies that elementary school heads practice collaborative conflict management style by attempting to deal with all the concerns of teachers to solve concerns and issues immediately.

Ghaffar et al., (2010) has the same recommendation that all the principals should adopt the best style of conflict management according to the situation. The respondents of their study preferred collaboration as conflict management style.

The level of conflict management styles of elementary school heads in terms of competing is as perceived by themselves is effective with the mean of 4.41.

The statement “am firm in pursuing my goals” ranked first with the mean of 4.62 described as effective; followed by “know when the outcome is critical and cannot be compromised”, with the mean of 4.57, described as effective. The statement “would argue my case and insist on the merits of my point of view” with the mean of 4.08 got the lowest rating.

For teachers the level of conflict management styles of elementary school heads in terms of competing is effective with the mean of 4.13.

The statement “am firm in pursuing my goals” ranked first with the mean of 4.33 described as effective; followed by “know when the outcome is critical and cannot be compromised” and “can figure out what needs to be done and I am usually right” with the mean of 4.22 described as effective.

The statement “would argue my case and insist on the merits of my point of view”, with the mean of 3.86 got the lowest rating.

This result reveals that competing is effective in resolving conflicts in school. The school heads are firm in their decision and use their power of command.

Result conforms with Pace (2013) who explained that the first conflict management style is that of the competitor or tough battler. This style is exemplified by the person who ambitiously realizes his/her goals at the expense of others.

The level of conflict management styles of elementary school heads got the lowest mean of 4.08 is avoiding as perceived by the school heads.

The statement “try to avoid creating unpleasantness for myself” and “avoid taking positions which could create controversy” ranked first with the mean of 4.27 described as effective; followed by “try to do what is necessary to avoid useless tensions” with the mean of 4.24 described as effective.

The statement “let others take responsibility for solving the problem” with the mean of 3.84 got the lowest rating.

Teachers gave their lowest rating to avoiding as conflict management style of the school heads with the mean of 3.93 described as effective.

The statement “try to do what is necessary to avoid useless tensions.” ranked first with the mean of 4.09 described as effective; followed by “try to avoid creating unpleasantness for myself” with the mean of 4.03 described as effective.

The statement “feel uncomfortable and anxious when the persons involved are closely related to me” with the mean of 3.72 got the lowest rating.

The findings imply that the least conflict resolution the school heads employ is avoiding eluding from taking positions and useless tensions that creates controversy.

This is similar with Deetz and Stevenson (2014) who proved that avoidance may be regarded as a negative strategy, in some cases it can be viewed as valuable. Avoidance can delay the discussion of the conflict until participants have "cooled down" and could be used positively when whether the issue is not really worth the effort.

The findings conform to Kilmann and Thomas (2015), they agreed that avoiding is unassertive and uncooperative when a person is avoiding he/she does not want to resolve her concerns or to solve other's concerns.

Table 2. Level of Conflict Management Styles of the Elementary School Heads As Perceived by Themselves and Elementary School Teachers

Statement	School Heads		Teachers	
	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
Collaborating	4.53	Very Effective	4.17	Effective
1. Attempt to deal with all of his and my concerns.	4.59	Very Effective	4.25	Effective
2. Attempt to get all concerns and issues immediately out in the open.	4.59	Very Effective	4.19	Effective
3. Tell him my ideas and ask him for his ideas.	4.51	Very Effective	4.23	Effective
4. Attempt to immediately work through our differences.	4.46	Effective	4.18	Effective
5. Lean toward a direct discussion of the problem	4.54	Very Effective	4.17	Effective
6. Am very often concerned with satisfying all our wishes.	4.51	Very Effective	4.09	Effective
8. Share the problem with the other persons so that we can work it out.	4.59	Very Effective	4.21	Effective
9. Explore issues with others so as to find solutions that meet everyone's needs.	4.54	Very Effective	4.13	Effective
10. Gather as much information as I can and keep the lines of communication open.	4.62	Very Effective	4.17	Effective
11. Try to see conflicts from both sides.	4.38	Effective	4.02	Effective
Competing	4.41	Effective	4.13	Effective
1. Am firm in pursuing my goals.	4.62	Very Effective	4.33	Effective
2. Try to win my position on the matter.	4.46	Effective	4.17	Effective
3. Make some effort to make things happen according to my judgment.	4.49	Effective	4.16	Effective
4. Know when the outcome is critical and cannot be compromised.	4.57	Very Effective	4.22	Effective
5. Try to show him the logic and benefits of my position.	4.43	Effective	4.18	Effective
6. Try to convince the other person of the virtues of my	4.35	Effective	4.09	Effective

position.				
7. Emphasize the power of my command.	4.35	Effective	4.16	Effective
8. Would argue my case and insist on the merits of my point of view.	4.08	Effective	3.86	Effective
9. find conflicts challenging and exhilarating	4.19	Effective	3.95	Effective
10. Can figure out what needs to be done and I am usually right.	4.54	Effective	4.22	Effective
Avoiding	4.08	Effective	3.93	Effective
1. Let others take responsibility for solving the problem.	3.84	Effective	3.90	Effective
2. Try to do what is necessary to avoid useless tensions.	4.24	Effective	4.09	Effective
3. Try to avoid creating unpleasantness for myself.	4.27	Effective	4.03	Effective
4. Try to postpone the issue until I have had some time to think it over.	3.97	Effective	3.88	Effective
5. Feel that the differences are not always worth worrying about.	3.97	Effective	3.96	Effective
6. Avoid taking positions which could create controversy.	4.27	Effective	3.99	Effective
7. Might try and appease the other's feelings and preserve our relationship.	4.22	Effective	4.01	Effective
8. Say a little and leave as soon as the issues have been heard.	4.11	Effective	3.90	Effective
9. Feel uncomfortable and anxious when the persons involved are closely related to me.	3.92	Effective	3.72	Effective
10. Avoid hard feelings by keeping my disagreements with others to myself.	4.03	Effective	3.82	Effective
Accommodating	4.33	Effective	4.11	Effective
1. try to stress those things upon which we both agree rather than negotiate the things on which we disagree	4.38	Effective	4.06	Effective
2. Try to appease the other's feelings and preserve our relationship.	4.30	Effective	4.15	Effective
3. Try to be considerate of the other person's wishes.	4.49	Effective	4.19	Effective
4. would try to meet his wishes if the other's position seems very important to him	4.27	Effective	3.97	Effective
5. might let him maintain his views if it makes the other person happy	4.43	Effective	4.20	Effective
6. Try to meet the expectations of others.	4.19	Effective	4.07	Effective
7. Try to accommodate the wishes of my friends and family.	4.08	Effective	3.99	Effective

11.value peace within the school rather than getting what he wants	4.54	Effective	4.22	Effective
Compromising	4.40	Effective	4.08	Effective
1. Try to find a compromised solution.	4.49	Effective	4.05	Effective
2. Sometimes sacrifice my own wishes for the wishes of the other person.	4.43	Effective	4.05	Effective
3. Consistently seek other's help in working out a solution.	4.46	Effective	4.14	Effective
4. Communicates clearly about his and our position on the matter.	4.46	Effective	4.17	Effective
5. Propose a middle ground.	4.35	Effective	3.98	Effective
6.try to find a fair combination of gains and losses for both of us	4.38	Effective	4.02	Effective
7. Try to find a position that is intermediate between his and mine.	4.32	Effective	4.02	Effective
8. Try to get him to settle for a compromised solution.	4.38	Effective	4.09	Effective
9. Propose an opinion that is acceptable to both parties.	4.49	Effective	4.16	Effective
10. Would meet people halfway to break deadlocks.	4.41	Effective	4.01	Effective
11. Negotiate and adopt a give-and-take approach to problem situations.	4.22	Effective	4.17	Effective
Overall Mean	4.35	Effective	4.08	Effective

Causes of Conflict

Table 3 presents the mean for the causes of conflict as perceived by the elementary school heads and teachers.

For school heads, **personality factors** as causes of conflict got the highest mean of 3.97. The statement "*Different personalities of various employees*", ranked first with a mean of 4.38 described as **frequently true**; followed by "*Balancing being the boss and being a friend*" with a mean of 4.19 described as **frequently true**.

The statement that got the lowest mean of 3.68 described as **frequently true** was "*Dealing with pressure and shifting priorities from my own boss and other higher ups.*"

For teachers' **personality factors** as causes of conflict got the highest mean of 3.99 described as **frequently true**. The statement "*Different personalities of various employees*" ranked first with a mean of 4.37 described as **frequently true**; followed by "*Balancing being the boss and being a friend*" with a mean of 4.03 described as **frequently true**. The statement got the lowest mean of 3.72 described as **frequently true** is "*Dealing with pressure and shifting priorities from my own boss and other higher ups.*"

This implies that the main cause of conflict in school is due to contributing **personality factors** as perceived by the respondents.

Kennedy (2012) supported the result that the sources of conflict include; shared resources, differences in goals, difference in perceptions and values, disagreements in the role requirements, nature of work activities, individual approaches, and the stage of organizational development.

Along power factors as causes of conflict, school heads perceived this as effective with the mean of 3.79 described as **frequently true**.

The statement "*Getting employees to understand and follow instructions*" ranked first with a mean of 4.22; followed by "*Ambiguity of duties and responsibilities and delegation of tasks*" with a mean of 4.11. The statement that got the lowest mean of 3.32 is "*Insufficient authority and discretion to reward high performers.*" All these results were described as **frequently true**.

Power factors ranked second as causes of conflict as perceived by teachers with the mean 3.68 described as **frequently true**. The statement "*Ambiguity of duties and responsibilities and delegation of tasks*" ranked first with a mean of 4.17; followed by "*Getting employees to understand and follow instructions*" with a mean of 3.81; the statement got the lowest mean of 3.34 is "*Giving negative feedback to employees regarding their performance.*"

All these statements obtained the descriptive rating of frequently **true**.

The study reveals that ambiguity of duties and responsibilities and teachers difficulty in understanding instructions were the sources of conflicts in school.

Mansor et al., (2012) also identified that conflict may originate from understanding the nature of tasks in the organization. It has been found that appropriate classification of conflict is beneficial to understand its nature and implication.

Conflict of interest ranked last as causes of conflict with the mean of 3.66 described as **frequently true** as perceived by the school heads.

The highest mean is noted in the statement "*Unawareness on the existing policies*" with a mean of 4.24; followed by "*Limited resources time, money, space, materials, supplies, and equipment are all valuable resources*" with a mean of 3.76. The statement got the lowest mean of 3.19 is "*Groups have formed within the team and are taking 'sides'.*"

Similarly, **conflict of interest** ranked last as cause of conflict with the mean of 3.60 described as **frequently true** as perceived by teachers.

The highest statement is noted in the statement "*Unawareness on the existing policies*" with a mean of 4.04; followed by "*Limited resources time, money, space, materials, supplies, and equipment are all valuable resources*" with a mean of 3.67.

The statement got the lowest mean of 3.31 is "*Primary responsibilities of teacher are compromised by other co-curricular activities*".

This implies that conflicts originate when teachers are unawareness on the existing policies resulting to conflict of interest.

Tonder and Lessing (2003) has similar findings, they asserted that increasing uncertainty and complexity in the operating environment of organizations provide fertile ground for the onset of conflict in the workplace.

Table 3. Mean Causes of Conflict As Perceived by the Elementary School Heads and Elementary School Teachers

Statement	School Heads		Teachers	
	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
Situational factors	3.74	Frequently True	3.63	Frequently True
1.Failure to communicate clearly resulting other teachers to resist the changes in the Department of Education	3.30	Frequently True	3.40	Frequently True
2. Managing people of a different generation.	4.16	Frequently True	3.88	Frequently True
3. Dealing with employees lack of basic skills	3.92	Frequently True	3.72	Frequently True
4. Managing people with a language gap.	3.68	Frequently True	3.52	Frequently True
5. Dealing with parents and the community	3.62	Frequently True	3.66	Frequently True
Personality factors	3.97	Frequently True	3.99	Frequently True
1.Different personalities of various employees	4.38	Frequently True	4.37	Frequently True
2. Interpersonal conflict on the team between and among individual employees and cliques who don't get along with each other.	3.81	Frequently True	3.92	Frequently True
3. Balancing being the boss and being a friend	4.19	Frequently True	4.03	Frequently True
4. Teachers with behavioral issues such as attendance, tardiness, personal issues, and conflict with coworkers.	3.81	Frequently True	3.93	Frequently True
5. Dealing with pressure and shifting priorities from my own boss and other higher ups.	3.68	Frequently True	3.72	Frequently True

Power factors	3.79	Frequently True	3.68	Frequently True
1. Insufficient authority and discretion to reward high performers.	3.32	Frequently True	3.44	Frequently True
2. Getting employees to understand and follow instructions	4.22	Frequently True	3.81	Frequently True
3. Teachers are too willing to agree with one another and do not have the confidence to express differing viewpoints.	3.46	Frequently True	3.63	Frequently True
4. Giving negative feedback to employees regarding their performance.	3.86	Frequently True	3.34	Frequently True
5. Ambiguity of duties and responsibilities and delegation of tasks	4.11	Frequently True	4.17	Frequently True
Conflict of interest	3.66	Frequently True	3.60	Frequently True
1.Groups have formed within the team and are taking “sides” On various issues.	3.19	Frequently True	3.59	Frequently True
2. Limited resources time, money, space, materials, supplies, and equipment are all valuable resources	3.76	Frequently True	3.67	Frequently True
3. Financial interests of an individual and proper utilization of fund	3.51	Frequently True	3.41	Frequently True
4. Primary responsibilities of teacher are compromised by other co-curricular activities	3.59	Frequently True	3.31	Frequently True
5.Unawareness on the existing policies	4.24	Frequently True	4.04	Frequently True
Overall Mean	3.79	Frequently True	3.73	Frequently True

Proposed Solution to Conflict

Table 4 presents the mean of proposed solution to conflict as perceived by the elementary school heads.

School heads gave highest rating to *respect and obedience* as solution to conflict with the mean of 4.43 described as frequently true. The statement “*treats teacher with respect in whatever circumstances*” ranked first with the mean of 4.76 described as almost always true; followed by “*appreciate their*

individual contribution in the context of overall success” with the mean of 4.54 also described as frequently true. The statements got the lowest mean of 4.14 described as frequently true is “*objectively understand what is behind the difficult person's actions rather than reacting right away*”.

Teachers’ perception is similar with the school heads, they gave highest rating to *respect and obedience* as solution to conflict with the mean of 4.19 described as frequently true.

The statement “*treats teacher with respect in whatever circumstances*” ranked first with the mean of 4.35; followed by “*appreciate their individual contribution in the context of overall success*” with the mean of 4.28 and the statement that got the lowest mean of 4.00 described as frequently true is “*try to adjust my priorities to accommodate teachers’ needs*”. These statements obtained mean rating described as frequently true.

This implies that respect and obedience is the key solution in handling conflict in schools.

The finding of this study is similar to what Ellis and Zabalak (2001) found wherein after investigation on the aspects of information and management, the component of openness as well as respect is vital in the organization. It was found that both the quantity and quality of information were significant and that both affected employees’ perceptions of organizational effectiveness.

The second variable that the elementary school heads perceived as frequently true with the mean of 4.34 is *sharing of goals and interest*.

The statement got the highest rating under this variable is “*promote a school culture with the spirit of unity*” with mean of 4.65; followed by “*involve my teachers when making significant changes in our school*” with mean of 4.59. While the statement got the lowest mean of 3.54 is “*give my teachers an equal opportunity to be heard regardless of their age and tenure*”.

For teachers, *sharing of goals and interests* ranked second with the mean of 4.15 described as frequently true. The statement got the highest rating under sharing of goals and interests is “*involve my teachers when making significant changes in our school*” with mean of 4.33; followed by “*establish supportive climate where teachers can openly discuss and understand each other’s ideas and concerns.*” with mean of 4.23. While the statement got the lowest mean of 3.87 is “*promote a school culture with the spirit of unity*”.

The results assert that promoting the spirit of unity by involving teachers in decision making has a great impact in addressing conflicts in organization.

This conforms to Messmer (2001) he proves that employees will work harder to reach goals if they’re involved in setting them. Employees resent being left out of the loop, especially when changes are going on, which can cause them to be cynical about future endeavors, their supervisors, and the company.

If kept uninformed, they may also assume the worst with their jobs at risk.

Values integration ranked last as proposed solution to conflict as perceived by the school heads with an overall mean of 3.72 described as frequently true. The statement that ranked first was “*accept criticism from my teachers*” with a mean of 4.05; followed by “*consider religious practices of my teachers*” with the mean of 4.03. While the statement that got the lowest overall mean of 3.38 was “*relate my actions to ethical sensibilities such as honesty, reliability and fairness*” all the mean ratings were described as frequently true.

Likewise, teachers also perceived *values integration* as the last proposed solution to conflict as shown by with the mean of 3.68 described as frequently true.

The statement that ranked first was “*consider religious practices of my teachers*” with the mean of 3.92; followed by “*accept criticism from my teacher*” with the mean of 3.81. and “*relate my actions to ethical sensibilities such as honesty, reliability and fairness*” mean of 3.48 described as also described as frequently true.

The findings imply that the least solution to resolve conflict was *values integration*.

Similarly, Tjosvold et al., (2014) supported the claim that values integration can also be used in facilitating open-minded discussions and constructive controversy.

Table 4. Proposed Solution to Conflict as Perceived By the Elementary School Heads and Elementary School Teachers

Statement	School Heads		Teachers	
	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
Improved communications	4.31	Frequently True	4.09	Frequently True
1.express anger constructively.	3.81	Frequently True	3.69	Frequently True
2. listen to each party's side of the story in an open and non-judgmental manner.	4.49	Frequently True	4.21	Frequently True
3. avoid harmful and negative statements.	4.35	Frequently True	4.17	Frequently True
4. address issues of concern at an early stage and seek constructive solutions.	4.46	Frequently True	4.22	Frequently True
5. ensure that there are regular opportunities for feedback on performance.	4.43	Frequently True	4.16	Frequently True
Values integration	3.72	Frequently True	3.68	Frequently True
1.decide based on moral standards	3.68	Frequently True	3.62	Frequently True
2.relate my actions to ethical sensibilities such as honesty, reliability and fairness	3.38	Frequently True	3.48	Frequently True

3.set goal that is compatible to values and beliefs of all teachers	3.49	Frequently True	3.56	Frequently True
4.accept criticism from my teacher	4.05	Frequently True	3.81	Frequently True
5.consider religious practices of my teachers	4.03	Frequently True	3.92	Frequently True
Respect and obedience	4.43	Frequently True	4.19	Frequently True
1. try to adjust my priorities to accommodate teachers' needs.	4.22	Frequently True	4.00	Frequently True
2.encourage my teachers to adjust to changing situations through innovation and creativity.	4.49	Frequently True	4.26	Frequently True
3.treats teacher with respect in whatever circumstances	4.76	Almost Always True	4.35	Frequently True
4.objectively understand what is behind the difficult person's actions rather than reacting right away.	4.14	Frequently True	4.08	Frequently True
5.appreciate their individual contribution in the context of overall success.	4.54	Almost Always True	4.28	Frequently True
Sharing of interests/goals	4.34	Frequently True	4.15	Frequently True
1. involve my teachers when making significant changes in our school.	4.59	Almost Always True	4.33	Frequently True
2. promote a school culture with the spirit of unity	4.65	Almost Always True	3.87	Frequently True
3. establish supportive climate where teachers	4.49	Frequently	4.23	Frequently

can openly discuss and understand each other's ideas and concerns.		True		True
4. provide them support, training and other needed resources	4.41	Frequently True	4.09	Frequently True
5. give my teachers an equal opportunity to be heard regardless of their age and tenure	3.54	Frequently True	4.21	Frequently True
Over all Mean	4.20	Frequently True	4.03	Frequently True

Level of Morale of Teachers

Table 5 presents the level of *morale of teachers* as perceived by the school heads and the teachers themselves. Among the variables being considered, the statement *"allows them to express freely"* ranked first with a mean of 4.49, described as **frequently true**; followed by *"creates positive atmosphere in the school"* 4.41 also described as **frequently true** and the lowest mean of 2.92 was obtained by the statement *"boost teacher's morale"* described as **occasionally true**.

Among the variables being considered, the statement *"motivates them to work harder and be more productive"* ranked first among the teachers with a mean of 4.16 described as **frequently true**; followed by *"creates positive atmosphere in the school"* with a mean of 4.13 also described as **frequently true**.

The least among the teachers was the statement *"lowers teacher's morale"* with a mean of 2.90 which was described as **occasionally true**.

This result implies that conflict management must give great consideration to the values and spirituality of the leader as well as the follower to lessen the conflicts.

Gibson (2011) study shows that teachers affirmed that spirituality and values in principal leadership could be positively influential when expressed appropriately and accompanied with integrity, quality care for others and professional competence.

Statement	School Heads		Teachers	
	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. Affects the relationship of my teachers with their colleagues.	4.00	Frequently True	3.75	Frequently True
2. increases their productivity in terms of performance.	4.00	Frequently True	4.07	Frequently True
3. may lead them role ambiguity	4.22	Frequently True	3.50	Frequently True

1. Affects the relationship of my teachers with their colleagues.	4.00	Frequently True	3.75	Frequently True
2. increases their productivity in terms of performance.	4.00	Frequently True	4.07	Frequently True
3.may lead them role ambiguity	4.22	Frequently True	3.50	Frequently True
4. May lead them to aggression, withdrawal and fixation.	3.54	Frequently True	3.20	Frequently True
5.lowers teacher's morale	3.05	Frequently True	2.90	Occasionally True
6.boost teacher's morale	2.92	Occasionally True	3.96	Frequently True
7.increases cooperation among my teachers	4.24	Frequently True	4.09	Frequently True
8.creates positive atmosphere in the school	4.41	Frequently True	4.13	Frequently True
9. Allows them to express freely.	4.49	Frequently True	4.08	Frequently True
10. satisfies their present teaching position	4.35	Frequently True	4.07	Frequently True
11.motivates them to work harder and be more productive	4.30	Frequently True	4.16	Frequently True
Overall Mean	3.96	Frequently True	3.81	Frequently True

Correlation between Profile and Conflict Management Styles of Elementary School Heads in Terms of Collaborating

The next table shows Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient r showing significant relationship between demographic profile of the elementary school heads and their conflict management styles in terms of collaborating.

Age, gender, highest degree earned and attendance to seminar and training related to conflict does not affect the conflict management of school heads in terms of collaborating.

This means that the null hypothesis that states there is no significant relationship between the demographic profile of the elementary school heads and their conflict management styles in terms of collaborating is accepted as revealed by their computed t -values which are within the critical value between -1.96 and 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance.

This implies that the demographic profile of the elementary school heads do not affect their conflict management styles in terms of collaborating.

This conforms with Vestal (2011), he explained that the profile such as gender has no significant relationship on collaborating.

Table 6a. Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient R Showing Significant Relationship between Demographic Profile of the Elementary School Heads and Their Conflict Management Styles in Terms of Collaborating

Profile	Pearson r	Df	Computed t-value	Tabular t-value ($\alpha=0.05$)	Decision
Age	0.06	35	0.33	1.96	H ₀ : accept
Gender	-0.04	35	-0.22	-1.96	H ₀ : accept
Highest degree earned	-0.09	35	-1.26	-1.96	H ₀ : accept
Attendance to seminar and training related to conflict management	-0.21	35	-1.26	1.96	H ₀ : accept

-1.96 < c.v. < 1.96

Correlation between Profile and Conflict Management Styles of Elementary School Heads in Terms of Competing

The next table shows Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient r showing significant relationship between demographic profile of the elementary school heads and their conflict management styles in terms of competing.

Age, gender, highest degree earned and attendance to seminar and training related to conflict does not affect the conflict management of school heads in terms of competing.

This means that the null hypothesis that states there is no significant relationship between the demographic profile of the elementary school heads and their conflict management styles in terms of competing is accepted as manifested by their computed t-values which are within the critical value between -1.96 and 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance.

This implies that the demographic profile of the elementary school heads do not affect their conflict management styles in terms of competing.

The specific findings derived from the table affirmed the findings published by Southern Nazarene University (2001), wherein demographics and conflict management styles (including competing style) do not have any correlation.

Table 6b. Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient R Showing Significant Relationship between Demographic Profile of the Elementary School Heads and Their Conflict Management Styles in Terms of Competing

Profile	Pearson r	Df	Computed t-value	Tabular t-value ($\alpha=0.05$)	Decision
Age	-0.13	35	-0.75	-1.96	H ₀ : accept
Gender	-0.06	35	-0.37	-1.96	H ₀ : accept
Highest degree earned	0.16	35	0.97	1.96	H ₀ : accept
Attendance to seminar and training related to conflict management	-0.22	35	-1.35	-1.96	H ₀ : accept

-1.96 < c.v. < 1.96

Correlation between Profile and Conflict Management Styles of Elementary School Heads in Terms of Avoiding

The next table shows Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient r showing significant relationship between demographic profile of the elementary school heads and their conflict management styles in terms of avoiding.

Age, gender, highest degree earned and attendance to seminar and training related to conflict has no relationship with the conflict management of school heads in terms of avoiding.

This means that the null hypothesis that states there is no significant relationship between the demographic profile of the elementary school heads and their conflict management styles in terms of avoiding is accepted as shown by their computed t -values which are within the critical value between -1.96 and 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance.

This implies that the demographic profile of the elementary school heads do not affect their conflict management styles in terms of avoiding.

Henkin et al., (2000) proved that there was no significant relationship between the conflict management strategies used by head teachers and demographic characteristics in terms of avoiding.

Vestal (2011) also explains that the profile such as gender has no significant relationship on conflict-management behaviors and have no significant effect on the prediction of avoiding.

Table 6c. Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient R Showing Significant Relationship between Demographic Profile of the Elementary School Heads and Their Conflict Management Styles in Terms of Avoiding

Profile	Pearson r	df	Computed t -value	Tabular t -value ($\alpha = 0.05$)	Decision
Age	0.07	35	0.40	1.96	H0: accept
Gender	0.08	35	0.49	1.96	H0: accept
Highest degree earned	0.05	35	0.32	1.96	H0: accept
Attendance to seminar and training related to conflict management	-0.02	35	-0.10	-1.96	H0: accept

$-1.96 < c.v. < 1.96$

Correlation between Profile and Conflict Management Styles of Elementary School Heads in Terms of Accommodating

The next table shows significant relationship between demographic profile of the elementary school heads and their conflict management styles in terms of accommodating.

Age, gender, highest degree earned and attendance to seminar and training related to conflict has no significant relationship with the conflict management of school heads in terms of accommodating.

This means that the null hypothesis that states there is no significant relationship between the demographic profile of the elementary school heads and their conflict management styles in terms of accommodating is accepted as shown by their computed t -values which are within the critical value between -1.96 and 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance.

This implies that the demographic profile of the elementary school heads do not affect their conflict management styles in terms of accommodating.

This findings is related with the result of Vestal (2011). He explains that the profile such as gender has no significant relationship on the prediction of accommodating.

Table 6d. Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient R Showing Significant Relationship between Demographic Profile of the Elementary School Heads and Their Conflict Management Styles in Terms of Accommodating

Profile	Pearson r	Df	Computed t-value	Tabular t-value ($\alpha= 0.05$)	Decision
Age	0.06	35	0.33	1.96	H ₀ : accept
Gender	-0.02	35	-0.12	-1.96	H ₀ : accept
Highest degree earned	0.08	35	0.46	1.96	H ₀ : accept
Attendance to seminar and training related to conflict management	0.19	35	1.14	1.96	H ₀ : accept

-1.96 < c.v. < 19.6

Correlation between Profile and Conflict Management Styles of Elementary School Heads in Terms of Compromising

The next table shows significant relationship between demographic profile of the elementary school heads and their conflict management styles in terms of compromising.

Age, gender, highest degree earned and attendance to seminar and training related to conflict has no significant relationship with the conflict management of school heads in terms of compromising.

This means that the null hypothesis that states there is no significant relationship between the demographic profile of the elementary school heads and their conflict management styles in terms of compromising is accepted as shown by their computed t-values which are within the critical value between -1.96 and 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance.

This implies that the demographic profile of the elementary school heads do not affect their conflict management styles in terms of compromising.

This in contrast with Mokhtarpour et al, (2013) they explain that there was a significant relationship between the principals' field of study and the choice of conflict solving styles in terms of compromising.

Table 6e. Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient R Showing Significant Relationship between Demographic Profile of the Elementary School Heads and Their Conflict Management Styles in Terms of Compromising

Profile	Pearson r	Df	Computed t-value	Tabular t-value ($\alpha= 0.05$)	Decision
Age	0.16	35	0.97	1.96	H ₀ : accept
Gender	0.03	35	0.19	1.96	H ₀ : accept
Highest degree earned	-0.06	35	-0.34	-1.96	H ₀ : accept
Attendance to seminar and training related to conflict management	-0.03	35	-0.15	-1.96	H ₀ : accept

-1.96 < c.v. < 19.6

Correlation between Conflict Management Styles of Elementary School Heads and Teachers' Morale

The next table reveals significant relationship between the conflict management styles of elementary school heads and teachers' morale.

The five conflict management styles of school heads: collaborating, competing, avoiding, accommodating and compromising have significant relationship with teachers' morale.

This means that the null hypothesis that states "there is no significant relationship between the conflict management styles of elementary school heads and the teachers' morale" was rejected as shown by their computed t-values which were not within the critical value between -1.96 and 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance.

The findings imply that the conflict management styles of elementary school heads in terms of collaborating, competing, avoiding, accommodating and compromising affect teachers' morale.

The findings of this study did not conform to Vokic and Sontor (2010), that proved that "there is no significant relationship between the conflict management styles of elementary school heads and the teachers' morale".

However, the findings support Henkin et al, (2000). Their study revealed that three conflict strategies had significant relationship with teachers' job satisfaction.

Compromising and accommodating were positively related with teachers' job satisfaction. Thus compromising and accommodating seemed to increase job satisfaction among the public primary school teachers.

Table 7. Korin's Correlation Showing Significant Relationship between the Conflict Management Styles of Elementary School Heads and the Teachers' Morale

Variable	Korin's	Df	Computed t-value	Tabular t-value ($\alpha = 0.05$)	Decision
Collaborating	0.98*	299	82.78	1.96	H ₀ : reject
Competing	0.98*	299	83.86	1.96	H ₀ : reject
Avoiding	0.98*	299	77.42	1.96	H ₀ : reject
Accommodating	0.98*	299	80.94	1.96	H ₀ : reject
Compromising	0.98*	299	81.84	1.96	H ₀ : reject

Correlation between the Causes of Conflict and Proposed Solutions in terms of Improved Communication

The next table shows the Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient r showing significant relationship between the causes of conflict and proposed solution as perceived by the school heads in terms of improved communication.

Of the four variables as causes of conflict, only personality factors affect the proposed solution in terms of improved communication as shown by the computed t-value of 3.09 which was greater than the tabular t-value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance.

This means that the null hypothesis that states "there is no significant relationship between the personality factors and proposed solution" was rejected in terms of improved communication.

The same null hypothesis is accepted in terms of situational, power factors and conflict of interest as manifested by their computed t-values which were within the critical value between -1.96 and 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance.

The study revealed that among causes of conflicts variables under personality factors affect the proposed solution to conflict in terms of communication.

Adejimola (2009) says that improved communication is an important non-violent means of resolving conflict and is important in promoting, preventing and resolving conflict situations.

Table 8a. Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient R Showing Significant Relationship on the Causes of Conflict and Proposed Solution As Perceived by the School Heads in Terms of Improved Communication

Variable	Pearson r	Df	Computed t-value	Tabular t-value ($\alpha= 0.05$)	Decision
Situational factors	0.10	35	0.60	1.96	H ₀ : accept
Personality factors	0.46*	35	3.09	1.96	H ₀ : reject
Power factors	0.26	35	1.58	1.96	H ₀ : accept
Conflict of interest	-0.01	35	-0.08	-1.96	H ₀ : accept

$-1.96 < c.v. < 19.6$

Correlation between the Causes of Conflict and Proposed Solutions in terms of Values Integration

The next table shows the Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient r showing significant relationship between the causes of conflict and proposed solution as perceived by the school heads in terms of values integration.

Of the four variables as causes of conflict, only conflict of interests affected the proposed solution in terms of values integration as shown by the computed t-value of 3.79 which was greater than the tabular t-value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance.

This means that the null hypothesis that states "*there is no significant relationship between the conflict of interest and proposed solution*" was rejected in terms of improved communication.

The same null hypothesis was accepted in terms of situational, personality and power factors as manifested by their computed t-values which were within the critical value between -1.96 and 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance.

The result of this study implies that among causes of conflicts, conflict of interests affect the proposed solution to conflict in terms of values integration.

Table 8b. Person Moment Correlation Coefficient R Showing Significant Relationship on the Causes of Conflict and Proposed Solution As Perceived by the School Heads in Terms of Values Integration

Variable	Pearson r	df	Computed t-value	Tabular t-value ($\alpha= 0.05$)	Decision
Situational factors	0.16	35	0.97	1.96	H ₀ : accept
Personality factors	-0.11	35	-0.63	-1.96	H ₀ : accept
Power factors	0.25	35	1.56	1.96	H ₀ : accept
Conflict of interest	0.54*	35	3.75	1.96	H ₀ : reject

-1.96 < c.v. < 19.6

Correlation between the Causes of Conflict and Proposed Solutions in terms of Respect and Obedience

The next table shows the Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient r showing significant relationship between the causes of conflict and proposed solution as perceived by the school heads in terms of **respect and obedience**.

Of the four variables as causes of conflict, only personality factors affect the proposed solution in terms of respect and obedience as shown by the computed t-value of 2.57 which was greater than the tabular t-value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance.

This means that the null hypothesis that states "*there is no significant relationship between the personality factors and proposed solution*" was rejected in terms of respect and obedience.

The same null hypothesis is accepted in terms of situational factors, power factors and conflict of interest as manifested by their computed t-values which are within the critical value between -1.96 and 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance.

The study revealed that among causes of conflicts variables under personality factors affect the proposed solution to conflict in terms of respect and obedience.

This was supported by Bodtker and Jameson (2001) who stated that one of the fundamental tenets of conflict resolution is that the parties in the conflict need to respect and understand each other's needs and perspectives.

This is not only understanding and respecting people that you agree with, but also attempting to understand and respect people that you disagree with, and respecting their right to disagree.

Table 8c. Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient R Showing Significant Relationship on The Causes of Conflict and Proposed Solution as Perceived by the School Heads in Terms of Respect and Obedience

Variable	Pearson r	df	Computed t-value	Tabular t-value ($\alpha= 0.05$)	Decision
Situational factors	-0.01	35	-0.07	-1.96	H ₀ : accept
Personality factors	0.40*	35	2.57	1.96	H ₀ : reject
Power factors	0.20	35	1.18	1.96	H ₀ : accept
Conflict of interest	0.00	35	-0.01	-1.96	H ₀ : accept

-1.96 < c.v. < 19.6

Correlation between the Causes of Conflict and Proposed Solutions in terms of Sharing of Interest and Goals

Table 8d shows the Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient r showing significant relationship between the causes of conflict and proposed solution as perceived by the school heads in terms of sharing of interests/goals.

Of the four variables as causes of conflict, only personality factors affected the proposed solution in terms of sharing of interests/goals as shown by the computed t-value of 2.80 which was greater than the tabular t-value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance.

This means that the null hypothesis that states "*there is no significant relationship between the conflict of interest and proposed solution*" was rejected in terms of sharing of interests/goals.

The same null hypothesis was accepted in terms of situational factors, power factors and conflict of interest as manifested by their computed t-values which were within the critical value between -1.96 and 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance.

The study revealed that among causes of conflicts variables under personality factors affected the proposed solution to conflict in terms of sharing of interests/goals.

The result was related with (Hughes, 2001) he explains that conflict resolution is based on the view that people have a right and an obligation to participate in decisions that affect their lives.

As such conflict resolution stresses that people are most likely to achieve their own goals and have rewarding relationships when they cooperate.

In the same vein, society will be more productive. This means that when in conflict, people should consider each other as allies in helping to create a solution to a common problem rather than enemies who are to be defeated.

Table 8d Person Moment Correlation Coefficient R Showing Significant Perceived Relationship on the Causes of Conflict and Proposed Solution as by the School Heads in Terms of Sharing of Interests/Goals

Variable	Pearson r	df	Computed t-value	Tabular t-value ($\alpha= 0.05$)	Decision
Situational factors	-0.03	35	-0.18	-1.96	H ₀ : accept
Personality factors	0.43*	35	2.80	1.96	H ₀ : reject
Power factors	0.19	35	1.14	1.96	H ₀ : accept
Conflict of interest	-0.09	35	-0.55	-1.96	H ₀ : accept

-1.96 < c.v. < 1.96

Respondents' Perception on the Significant Difference of Conflict Management of Elementary School Heads

Table 9 presents t-test showing significant difference on the perception of the elementary school heads and elementary school teachers in terms of conflict management styles of the elementary school heads.

The table shows that elementary school heads and elementary teachers has similar perception in terms of conflict management of school heads as shown by their computed t-value of 1.21 which is less than the tabular t-value of 2.02 at 0.05 level of significance.

This means that the null hypothesis "*there is no significant difference between the perception of elementary school heads and elementary teachers in terms of avoiding*" was accepted.

The same null hypothesis was rejected in terms of *collaborating, competing, accommodating and compromising* as manifested by their computed t-values which were all greater than the tabular t-value at 0.05 level of significance.

In other words, the elementary school heads and elementary teachers differ in their perception on conflict management styles of elementary school heads in terms of collaborating, competing, accommodating and compromising.

The result implies that elementary school heads and teacher have different perceptions in conflict managements in terms of collaborating, competing, accommodating and compromising while they have similar perspective in terms of avoiding.

This finding was fairly similar to the study by Patana (2003), where the deans conflict management styles, as rated by the deans themselves, were avoiding, collaborating, compromising.

As rated by the teachers, the dean's conflict management styles were accommodating, collaborating, and compromising.

Both school administrators and teachers depending on the purpose and situation utilize different or various conflict management styles in educative institutions.

Table 9. T-Test Showing Significant Difference on the Perception of the Elementary School Heads and Elementary School Teachers in Terms Of Conflict Management Styles of the Elementary School Heads

Variable		Mean	Df	Computed t-value	Tabular t-value	Decision
Collaborating*	School heads	4.53	55	3.93	2.00	H ₀ : reject
	School teachers	4.17				
Competing*	School heads	4.41	57	3.78	2.00	H ₀ : reject
	School teachers	4.13				
Avoiding	School heads	4.08	44	1.21	2.02	H ₀ : accept
	School teachers	3.93				
Accommodating*	School heads	4.33	48	2.22	2.01	H ₀ : reject
	School teachers	4.11				
Compromising*	School heads	4.40	53	3.31	2.00	H ₀ : reject
	School teacher	4.08				

c.v. < 2.00

Respondents' Perception on the Significant Difference on the Causes to Conflict

Table 10a presents the significant difference on the causes of conflict as perceived by the school heads and school teachers.

The table shows that the perception of school heads and teachers had no significant difference on the causes of conflict in terms of situational factors as shown by their computed t-value of 0.5987 which was lower than the tabular t-value of 2.45 at 0.05 level of significance.

This means that the null hypothesis that *“there is no significant difference between the perception of school heads and teachers on causes and solution to conflict in terms of situational factors”* was accepted. In other words, the elementary school heads had similar perception on the causes and solution to conflict in terms of situational factors.

The perception of school heads and teachers had no significant difference on the causes of conflict in terms of **personality factors** as shown by their computed t-value of -0.1187, which was within the tabular t-value of -2.31 at 0.05 level of significance.

This means that the null hypothesis that *“there is no significant difference between the perception of school heads and teachers on causes and solution to conflict in terms of personality factors”* was accepted. In other words, the elementary school heads has similar perception on the causes and solution to conflict in terms of **personality factors**.

There is no significant difference on the causes of conflict in terms of power factors as shown by their computed t-value of 0.5080 which is within the tabular t-value of 2.31 at 0.05 level of significance.

This means that the null hypothesis that *“there is no significant difference between the perception of school heads and teachers on causes and solution to conflict in terms of power factors”* was accepted. In other words, the elementary school heads had similar perception on the causes and solution to conflict in terms of power factors. The data reveals that there was no significant difference on the causes of conflict in terms of conflict of interest as shown by their computed t-value of 0.2676 which was within the tabular t-value of 2.36 at 0.05 level of significance.

This means that the null hypothesis that *“there is no significant difference between the perception of school heads and teachers on causes and solution to conflict in terms of conflict of interest”* was accepted. This also means that the elementary school heads had the same perception on the causes and solution to conflict in terms of conflict of interest.

This findings contradict with (Bader 2009), who stated that conflict differs when individuals struggle with differences in goals, abilities and aptitudes.

Table 10a. T-Test Showing Significant Difference on the Causes of Conflict as Perceived by the School Heads and School Teachers

Causes of conflict		Mean	Df	Computed t-value	Tabular t-value	Decision
Situational Factors	School heads	3.74	6	0.5987	2.45	H ₀ : accept
	School teachers	3.63				
Personality Factors	School heads	3.97	8	-0.1187	-2.31	H ₀ : accept
	School teachers	3.99				
Power Factors	School heads	3.79	8	0.5080	2.31	H ₀ : accept
	School teachers	3.68				
Conflict of interest	School heads	3.66	7	0.2676	2.36	H ₀ : accept
	School teachers	3.60				

Respondents' Perception on the Significant Difference on the Proposed Solution to Conflict

Table 10b presents the significant difference on the proposed solution to conflict as perceived by the school heads and school teachers.

The table shows that the perception of school heads and teachers has no significant difference on the proposed solution in terms of improved communication as shown by their computed t-value of 1.34 which is lower than the tabular t-value of 2.31 at 0.05 level of significance.

This means that the null hypothesis that *"there is no significant difference between the perception of school heads and teachers on proposed solution to conflict in terms of improved communication"* was accepted.

The result implies that elementary school heads had similar perception on the proposed solution to conflict in terms of improved communication.

The computed t- value of 0.27 was within the tabular t-value of 2.45 at 0.05 level of significance. This indicated that perception of school heads and teachers had no significant difference on the proposed solution in terms of values integration.

The null hypothesis that *"there is no significant difference between the perception of school heads and teachers on proposed solution to conflict in terms of values integration"* was accepted. This states that elementary school heads and teachers have similar perception on the proposed solution to conflict in terms of values integration.

Moreover, there is no significant difference on the proposed solution in terms of respect and obedience as shown by their computed t-value of 1.78 which was lower than the tabular t-value of 2.45 at 0.05 level of significance.

This means that the null hypothesis that *"there is no significant difference between the perception of school heads and teachers on the proposed solution to conflict in terms of respect and obedience"* was accepted.

This proves that the elementary school heads and teachers have the same perception on the proposed solution to conflict in terms of respect and obedience.

The data reveals that there was no significant difference on the proposed solution in terms of sharing of interest and goal as shown by their computed t-value of 0.87 which is lower than the tabular t-value of 2.58 at 0.05 level of significance.

This means that the null hypothesis that *"there is no significant difference between the perception of school heads and teachers on proposed solution to conflict in terms of sharing of interest and goal"* was accepted.

This also means that the elementary school heads had the same perception on the proposed solution to conflict in terms of sharing of interest and goal.

The result of this study is in contrast with that of Crossfield and Bourne (2018), who indicated that the perception of school principal and teacher respondents had significant difference in terms of integrating as a solution in managing conflict in schools.

Table 10b. T-Test Showing Significant Difference on the Proposed Solution to Conflict as Perceived by the School Heads and School Teachers

Causes of conflict		Mean	Df	Computed t-value	Tabular t-value	Decision
Improved Communication	School head	4.31	8	1.34	2.31	H ₀ : accept
	School teacher	4.09				
Values Integration	School head	3.72	6	0.27	2.45	H ₀ : accept
	School teacher	3.68				
Respect and Obedience	School head	4.43	6	1.78	2.45	H ₀ : accept
	School teacher	4.19				
Sharing of interests and goals	School head	4.54	5	0.87	2.58	H ₀ : accept
	School teacher	4.15				

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn.

1. The respondents vary in their demographic profile. Three or 8.11 percent of the school heads were bachelor's degree holder while 117 or 44.32 percent of teachers has the same educational qualification. Majority of them attended limited conflict management seminars.
2. **Collaborating** is evident and the dominating conflict management style among elementary school heads while they also claimed that **avoiding** is an effective conflict management style.
3. The common causes of conflict in school are related to personality factors due to different personality of various teachers.
4. Respect and obedience is the dominant solution in managing conflict.
5. Conflict management styles influence teachers' morale.
6. The demographic profile of the school heads has no significant relationship with the conflict management style stated in this study.
7. Conflict management styles of elementary school heads allow the teachers to express themselves freely.
8. The causes of conflict related to personality factors affect the proposed solution in terms of improved communication, respect and obedience and sharing of interests/ goals.
9. The respondents had similar perception in terms of **collaborating, competing, accommodating and compromising** as conflict management styles of elementary school heads.
10. The perception of elementary school heads and teachers were similar in terms of causes of conflicts and proposed solution.

Recommendations

For the Department of Education

1. The Department of Education should design seminars and trainings related to conflict management to equip the school heads in handling conflict.
2. Monitor the process of school heads in handling conflict. Monitoring will serve as the basis in designing seminars and training.

For the School Heads

1. School heads should pursue their graduate studies to enhance their conflict management style in handling teachers with different personalities.
2. Use **collaborating** conflict management styles in handling conflict rather than avoiding.
3. Include interpersonal skills and values related training in *School Learning Action Cell* session to educate the teachers in handling conflict within their level.
4. Conduct team building to establish camaraderie among teachers and minimize the occurrence of conflict related to personality factors.
5. Confront conflict based on moral standards giving consideration to values and beliefs of all teachers.
6. Utilize the findings of this study to strengthen their skills in managing conflict because it highly affects the teachers' morale.

For Teachers

1. Subscribe online inspirational and motivational channels to improve their interpersonal skills.
2. Focus on the effective delivery of learning and maintain good relationship with coworkers.
3. Attend trainings related to interpersonal skills and values related trainings.

For Future Researchers

Conduct and validate other variables that were limited in this study.

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